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DEMAND FORM MANAGEMENT GRADATES: BEYOND THE CURRICULUM**Kadambini Kumari**

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Abstract:

Management education system in India is initiated in 19th century. India's first B-school i.e. Commercial School of Pacchiappa Charties was set up in 1886 in the southern city of Chennai (Madras). Approximately 129 years journey revolutionized the system requirement & expectation of the companies from the management graduates. This pare is discussing the current B-School scenario, expectation from graduated by corporates & the Gap exist between demand & supply. The big gap was identified in Skill development & right attitude of an individual's towards learning, accepting chance & work further to expertise.

Keyword: *Management education; Management Skill, Attitudes*

Present Scenario:

Corporates are looking for both intellect, consistency in performances across your education and professional backgrounds and skills relevant to their business. It is more about your fitment to the needs of the corporate as well as how the person can be molded to what the corporate is looking for.

Hiring Demand Up for Business Graduates

Employer demand for graduate business students across all candidate types is on the rise this year, both globally and by world region. More companies report plans to hire recent business school graduates in 2014 compared with actual hiring in 2013. n Four in five (80%) companies plan to hire MBAs, up from 73 percent in 2013. n More companies plan to hire Master in Management graduates (50% in 2014, up from 45% in 2013). n More employers are seeking Master of Accounting graduates (45% in 2014, up from 36% in 2013). n Demand is also increased for Master of Finance candidates (44% in 2014, up from 39% in 2013).

Employer Hiring Trends Mirror Growth and Productivity Goals

In 2014, as economic conditions worldwide have recovered, more companies are increasingly focused on improved performance and productivity and hiring business graduates to sustain and strengthen their growth. Regional hiring trends mirror organizational goals. In Asia-Pacific, more companies will hire recent business school graduates compared with last year, with the greatest hiring growth expected for graduates of specialized master's programs in management, accounting, and finance. Asia-Pacific companies are shifting away from economic challenges and cost reduction goals and placing more focus on growth goals. Forty-five percent of companies are planning to launch new products in 2014 (up from 37% in 2013). n A greater proportion of European companies plans to hire recent MBA, Master in Management, and Master of Accounting graduates in 2014 compared with 2013. Although fewer European companies are focused on cost reduction goals (39% of companies this year compared with 52% in 2013), the percentage of companies with plans for growth and expansion will be similar to 2013. In the United States, there is modest growth in the hiring outlook for business school graduates in 2014. While MBA talent remains the dominant source of business school hires among US companies, employers this year foresee growth in specialized business master's (non-MBA) hires.

MBA Compensation in 2014 Comparable to Last Year This year, a majority of companies worldwide will offer recent MBA graduates starting salaries comparable to those offered in 2013, with the exception of employers in the Asia-Pacific region. The median base salary for recent MBA graduates in the Asia-Pacific region in 2014 is US\$21,000. The majority of Asia-Pacific employers (62%) plan to increase MBA base salaries at the rate of inflation

(31%) or above (31%), compared with 2013. n The median base salary for recent MBAs in Europe in 2014 is US\$69,000, and reflects a salary premium of US\$28,000 over expected starting pay for recipients of bachelor's degrees, who will earn a median of US\$41,000. n The projected median base salary for MBAs in the United States in 2014 is US\$95,000. This represents a US\$45,000 premium over recent bachelor's-degree recipients, who will earn a median of US\$50,000.

Communication Skills Top Sought-After Proficiencies in New Hires

New this year, employers were asked to evaluate not only which skill sets are most important when considering job candidates to hire, but the level of skill proficiency they require for placing candidates in a mid-level job. Employers seek recent graduates who are highly proficient in communication skills, specifically oral communication, followed by listening and writing skills. On average, employers ranked communications skills twice as important as managerial skills.

Requirements change as markets change

Employers' recruitment operations are becoming much more short-term in response to fast-changing markets and technologies. Companies frequently look for specific mixes of skills, and the mix can change rapidly.

In the mid-1990s, for example, there was a strong demand for German-speaking MBA graduates which could be traced to a number of leading German companies wanting to introduce a more international culture and the need to expand into east European countries, where German is widely spoken. This was followed by a demand for graduates able to work effectively in the fast-growing markets of China and the Pacific Rim, where candidates needed residence qualifications as well as the appropriate languages.

Expectation

They must be committed, dedicated, self-disciplined, self-motivated, showing an aptitude and willingness to learn. They must possess strong analytic, listening, and communication skills, and they must be able to work in a team and collaborate. Finally, they must come in with at least a basic knowledge of the organization and processes within the organization, and an understanding of products, solutions, and services. Curriculum is minimal & than the skill & right attitude which are more important to corporate which they look in fresher graduates. They

can give further training on developing knowledge to the individuals with right attitude & having basic skill set to perform.

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